

DIGITAL DIVIDE IN INDIA: AN OBSTACLE TO ACHIEVE INCLUSIVE & EQUITABLE EDUCATION

Dr. Ambili Madhu Thampi

Assistant Professor,

Department Of Economics,

K.P.B. Hinduja College of Commerce, Charni Road, Mumbai.

Abstract:

The development of a nation depends upon its educated and healthy labour force. Human developments indicators to a great extent play an important role in spearheading the development process of a nation. Of the various human development indicators, education needs special mention as it is a driving factor which can lead to healthy and skilled workforce capable enough to earn better income as well. UN Sustainable Development Goal 4 stresses on the importance to ensure an inclusive and equitable quality education. But the unexpected covid-19 pandemic has struck various sectors of the economy including the education sector delaying the achievement of this goal. This study tries to investigate the obstacles in the form of disparities which exist in education sector and to explore the digital divide which exist among rural-urban areas and between sex using secondary data from NSS and TRAI as well as suggest possible measures to deal with the problems. Variables like Net Attendance Ratio, Dropout Rates, Computer and Internet facility available etc. were used to carry out the study.

Key terms: *Digital divide, Net Attendance Ratio, Dropouts, Disparities, Gross Attendance Ratio*

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Introduction:

Education is a major driving force of development in any modern society and its significance is widely accepted. It acts as a catalyst in development of a nation and henceforth help in achieving sustainable, just, equal and all-inclusive peaceful societies.

As the popular quote says that the ‘destruction of a nation does not require any atom bombs or missiles. Instead, lowering the quality of education by allowing students to cheat in examination is sufficient to demolish it.’ Provision of good quality all-inclusive education to the population, especially the younger generations can enhance their productive capacity, innovative as well as critical thinking and problem solving abilities which in turn can lead to the socioeconomic progress of a nation. The United Nation’s Sustainable Development Goal¹- 4, gives special mention as to the significance of achieving an inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting life-long learning opportunities for all. In order to achieve inclusive education, differences that exist across sex, areas, caste, religion, geographical location etc. need to be narrowed down. But these discrepancies should be narrowed to achieve a balanced society capable enough to solve problems using innovative solutions and tools. But the covid-19 pandemic has extensively brought about changes in the education sector along with various other sectors.

Statement of the Problem

The covid-19 pandemic has caused the largest disruption in the education sector starting from school education to higher and technical education. Apart from the loss in terms of learning, the economic impact on households can possibly widen the disparity in educational achievement. India has been implementing various remote education programmes to keep up learning during the pandemic time. However, for the successful implementation of these schemes, the young population should have adequate digital literacy as well as access to various equipment’s like smart phones, computers, TV, radio and internet connectivity irrespective of sex, age, and spatial differences. The pandemic has widened the inequities and students have to deal with the digital divide which acts as a barrier to their educational attainment which in turn has detained the objective of achieving the fourth SDG put forth by the United Nations.

The present study is an attempt to find out the disparities which exist across sex and rural –urban areas in India. It also tries to look into the digital divide in education in terms of digital infrastructure like computer and internet facilities available to people across sex and rural-urban areas as it can finally impact the educational attainment during the pandemic phase. The period of the present study ranges from 2017-18 to 2019-20.

¹ United Nations (2020). The [UN Sustainable Development Summit](#) held in New York in September 2015, put forth 17 Sustainable Development Goals to be achieved by the signatory countries by the year 2030

Objectives

1. To understand the disparity in education across rural-urban areas and between males and females.
2. To identify the digital divide across sex and rural-urban areas.
3. To suggest measures to deal with these disparities.

Data Source and Methodology

The study has used secondary data from print and electronic media, especially the National Sample Survey and Telecom Regulatory Authority of India data. Various indicators like Net Attendance Ratio, dropout rate, availability of computer, internet facilities; internet subscription data etc. has been used to conduct the analysis.

Education in India before the covid-19 pandemic in India

Education being one of the important human development indicators, its influence on the socioeconomic development of any country is immense. In order to understand the situation in education sector in terms of selected indicators during the pandemic period, it is imperative to understand the pre pandemic scenario which has been analyzed using NSS.

Percentage of persons with 15 years and above by highest level of education completed by sex and area gives a rough estimate regarding education level achieved by the people above the said age. Even though these figures do not represent the age specific education level, still it gives a rough idea with respect to the differences in educational attainment across spatial units and gender.

Source: NSS Report No.585: Household Social Consumption on Education in India

The figure clearly shows that larger percentages of urban people have completed higher levels of education from secondary level on wards, irrespective of sex and the figures are favorable to men compared to women at higher levels of education in both rural and urban areas. Consequently, another notable feature is that percentage of illiteracy is highest among females compared to males in both rural and urban areas even though the illiteracy percentage is less in urban areas. All these clearly highlight the disparity which exists in rural areas and among women and the obstacle behind achieving inclusiveness in educational progress.

The continuity in education can be understood from the Net Attendance Ratio² which is a better measure than the Gross Attendance Ratio³.

$$\text{NAR for I to V} = \frac{\text{Number of persons of age 6–10 currently attending classes I–V}}{\text{Estimated population in the age–group 6–10 years}} \times 100$$

Source: NSS Report No.585: Household Social Consumption on Education in India

The graph clearly indicates that the Net Attendance Ratio is high in urban areas for both sex and at the same time it is better for males in both areas compared to women's, the exception being upper primary and secondary level education in urban areas. Moreover,

² Net attendance ratio (NAR) for a particular level of education is the ratio of the number of persons in the official age-group attending that level of education to the total number persons in that age-group.

³ The gross attendance ratio (GAR) is the total number of students attending primary school, irrespective of age and expressed as a percentage of the official primary school-age population.

an important fact to be noted is that at higher levels of education, Net Attendance Ratio is declining. The fall in attendance can be due to various reasons shown below.

Table 1: Percentage of ever enrolled persons of age 3 to 35 years currently not attending education by major reasons (2017-18)

Indicator		Rural		Urban		Rural+ Urban	
		Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
Percentage of ever enrolled persons currently not attending education		41.3	40	46.2	47.8	42.7	42.2
Percentage distribution of ever enrolled persons by major reason for currently not attending	Not interested in education	20.6	15.9	14.9	12.6	18.8	14.8
	Financial constraints	25.6	18.4	21.4	16.1	24.3	17.7
	Engaged in domestic activities	4.7	31.9	2.3	26.7	4	30.2
	Engaged in economic activities	34.9	4.4	41.5	7.3	36.9	5.3
	School is far off	0.6	3.3	0.1	1.2	0.5	2.7
	Timings of educational institutions not suitable	0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0	0.1
	Medium of instruction used unfamiliar	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1
	Inadequate number of teachers	0	0.1	0	0	0	0
	Quality of teachers not satisfactory	0.1	0.1	0	0	0.1	0.1
	Route to educational institution not safe	0	0.2	0	0.1	0	0.2
	Unable to cope up with studies/failure in studies	4.1	3.7	3.1	2.6	3.8	3.4
	Unfriendly atmosphere at school	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1
	Completed desired level/class	4.2	4.2	9.5	11.2	5.8	6.4
	Preparation for competitive examination	1.8	0.6	3.2	1.9	2.2	1
	Non-availability of female teacher		0.1		0.1		0.1
	Non-availability of girls' toilet		0.1		0.1		0.1
	Marriage		12.4		15		13.2
	Others	3.1	4.4	3.6	4.9	3.3	4.5
all	100	100	100	100	100	100	

Source: NSS Report No.585: Household Social Consumption on Education in India

Engagement of women in domestic activities has been one of the major reasons among females for not attending education irrespective of rural or urban areas whereas in the case of men, the major reason has been involvement in economic activities. The percentage of men engaged in economic activities is higher in urban areas compared to rural areas especially due to the better job opportunities available there. In short, financial difficulties, lack of interest in education, involvement in economic activities and domestic responsibilities were the factors which mainly led the enrolled students from not attending educational institutions. The declining attendance can eventually end up in dropout.

Dropout

An ever-enrolled person was considered a dropout if that person did not complete the last level of education for which enrolled and currently not attending any educational institution due to reasons other than ‘completion of the desired level of education’. The following graph clearly indicates the percentage of dropouts among ever enrolled persons of age 3 to 35 years by level of last enrollment.

Source: NSS Report No.585: Household Social Consumption on Education in India

Percentage of dropout is less in urban areas compared to rural areas at various levels of education. But a notable fact is that the dropout percentage is the highest at secondary level in both urban and rural areas followed by upper primary level and is the lowest at higher levels of education especially at post-graduation and above. Lesser dropout rates

in urban areas are indicative of the better awareness among people regarding the significance of education. Better enrollment and continuity at higher levels of education can be ensured by reducing the dropout rates at lower levels of education. This can be achieved by creating better awareness regarding the benefits of higher education and provide various incentives like scholarships, free books, travelling facilities, boarding facilities etc. to the under privileged sections which in turn can promote inclusiveness and equality.

Availability of Computer and internet facility

Covid-19 pandemic has completely revamped the educational system as physical learning became impossible and educational institutions had to follow the virtual mode of instruction in order to ensure continuous education to the beneficiaries. In this context, the availability of adequate digital infrastructure and internet facility became very essential to carry out uninterrupted learning to the students concerned.

In this situation, the percentage of households with computer and internet facility needs to be taken into account to get an idea regarding the access to virtual mode of education. The following figure clearly shows the percentage of households with computer and internet facilities during 2017-18, much before the pandemic hit the world. Rural urban disparity is clearly visible from the figure, which clearly shows that the rural households were much behind the urban areas with respect to availability of computer and internet facility.

Source: NSS Report No.585: Household Social Consumption on Education in India

Mere availability of computer and internet facility cannot ensure its usage. The following figure depicts the percentage of people aged 5 years and above who are capable enough to use computer and internet.

Source: NSS Report No.585: Household Social Consumption on Education in India

Computer includes devices like desktop, laptop, notebook, netbook, palmtop and tablet (or similar handheld devices). However, smartphone was not included in the computer. But the percentage of internet users were larger than the computer users indirectly pointing out on the large share of mobile phone users which was prominent in the case of both urban areas and males compared to rural areas and females respectively, emphasizing on digital disparity.

The digital divide between rural and urban areas had been very prominent even before the pandemic hit, which hitherto can adversely affect the educational attainment of people in rural areas especially after the novel corona virus hit the world. Countries including India had been trying ways to continue the provision of education during the pandemic year by adopting digital method of functioning as the new normal. But for the successful implementation of digital mode of education, access to adequate digital infrastructures and internet connectivity at affordable rates to various sections of population at both rural and urban areas need to be ensured. The situation of India in terms of digital facilities accessed during 2019 to 2021 can be understood from the following table.

Source: Telecom Regulatory Authority of India, 2020

The number of subscribers both wired and wireless is higher in urban areas compared to rural areas in all the years confirming the existing disparity in availability of digital facilities and hence the pronounced digital divide between these areas in terms of digital infrastructure. Majority of the total subscribers belong to the wireless category compared to wire line subscribers stressing on the use of smart phones and flexible internet services. The decline in the use of wireless and wire line subscribers in India over the years can be due to relinquishing multiple wireless connections, surrender of wired connection or migration.

Source: Calculated from Telecom Regulatory Authority of India data

The annual percentage growth rate of internet subscribers across rural and urban areas over the years has increased depicting increased usage of mobile and other digital instruments. This can be due to the Government policies promoting more of digital transactions. The increased demand for digital usage arising from work from home and digital methods of education adopted during the pandemic has also led to positive growth rate during 2019-20. But even though growth rate has been increasing, there still existed huge digital divide between urban and rural areas.

Suggestions and Conclusions

The study on educational attainment in terms of selected indicators during the pre-pandemic and pandemic period shows that there existed disparities in education across sex and rural urban areas even before the pandemic. Online mode of imparting education as well as the work from home mode adopted by employers resulted in an increase in the number of wireless subscribers in both rural and urban areas and an increased growth rate of internet users. The data clearly threw light on the disparities faced by women and rural people in terms of educational variables and digital facilities that could curtail the delivery of virtual education, reducing the educational attainment of these groups which is a matter of concern for the government.

Education being one of the primary determinants of human development in a country, it should be made available to various sections of the population in an equitable manner. Proper care should be taken to eliminate the disparities in terms of provision of educational facilities to people. One of the major difficulties faced by the people especially the young population with respect to attainment of education during the pandemic time has been the inadequate access to education due to lack of availability and accessibility to various digital infrastructure, equipment and platforms. The Government should provide adequate digital infrastructure and facilities to people belonging to the rural areas, unprivileged and low income groups to enable them to pursue higher education and thereby bringing in inclusivity and equal opportunity. In order to promote the knowledge sharing and learning via digital platforms like DIKSHA, SWAYAM etc., the government should expand and develop adequate digital infrastructure in interior rural areas as well and facilities should be made available to various sections of population at an affordable price. Digital inclusion is one of the very essential method, especially during the time of pandemic to ensure that education reaches various sections of the people in an equitable manner which can lead to a just and balanced society.

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